

D1.2 Eco-design of Fatigue4Light materials

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Executive summary

In this report, the methodological framework that supports the integrated eco-design of electrical vehicle components is applied. Aspects that present a potential critical environmental performance are identified as hotspots. Eco-design strategies and specific actions are recognized towards the reduction of these potential environmental results. Strategies and actions are studied for each of the life cycle stages: Production (raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly); Use (energy consumption, driving cycle); and End-of-life (final waste management). Compiling the results from a dedicated webinar including an analytic hierarchy process, a ranking of the more significant and suitable actions for the eco-design of electrical vehicle components is presented.

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List of abbreviations

<i>AHP</i>	<i>Analytic Hierarchy Process</i>
<i>EV</i>	<i>Electric Vehicles</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>CRM</i>	<i>Critical Raw Materials</i>
<i>LCA</i>	<i>Life Cycle Analysis</i>
<i>LCC</i>	<i>Life Cycle Cost</i>
<i>PDSA</i>	<i>Plan-Do-Study-Act</i>

Introduction

Fatigue4Light Work Package (WP) 1 focuses on the selection of material candidates that could allow a reduction in the weight of the chassis part in 24-30%, considering technical requirements, eco-design and critical raw material selection.

In consequence, the consortium has been implicated on the holistic approach and participated on a working group specifically aimed at applying the eco-design methodology described in Deliverable 1.1 and at generating a set of strategies and specific actions of eco-design.

The results of the application of the eco-design methodology described in D1.1 are presented in this report. Conclusions of this report will enable the application of circular economy strategies and actions as requirements and guidelines for the development of new lightweight chassis parts.

Attainment of the objectives and explanation of deviations

The deliverable is fully in line with the contractual obligations and the project objectives. There is no time and content deviation.

The four key different steps stated in D1.1 (Figure 1) have been applied and results will be presented in the next sections.

Figure 1. Eco-design framework under FATIGUE4LIGHT project

1. STEP 1. Identification of Hotspots and Life Cycle Stages

A list of the most relevant issues related to the environmental performance of EVs is presented in this section.

An assessment of the state-of-the-art on conventional technologies and methods provided a preliminary benchmark assessment that helped identify the life cycle stages and the main aspects

that could influence and end up with a higher environmental burden, these aspects are also called hotspots.

Within a systematic design approach, hotspot identification represents an elemental step as it reveals the importance of different aspects to consider (3).

Even though, there is no standard process to characterize hotspots in Fatigue4Light methodology, first step includes initiating a qualitative assessment by selecting the system's concepts from the current available technologies, focusing on the identification and evaluation of hotspots along the entire life cycle (from raw material extraction to the end-of-life stage).

Hotspots and main issues were identified and characterized in relation to the different life cycle stages and are presented in the following tables, including an impact range that reflects the importance of this stage in the complete life cycle. This range is based on the results of a review of previous studies and are bestowed in a dedicated subsection for references.

Raw material extraction, manufacturing and assembly

Hotspots	EV production impacts are more significant than conventional vehicles (Hawkins et al 2012)
	Use of CRMs increases energy density (Shu et al 2020)
	Production of structural parts has a valuable contribution (Messagie et al 2010)
	New component molds can increase manufacturing cost (Volkan et al 2019)
Impact Range	35-50%
References	<p>Hawkins TR, Singh B, Majeau-Bettez G, Strømman AH. Comparative Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Conventional and Electric Vehicles. <i>J Ind Ecol.</i> 2013;17(1):53–64.</p> <p>Shu X, Guo Y, Yang W, Wei K, Zhu G. Life-cycle assessment of the environmental impact of the batteries used in pure electric passenger cars. <i>Energy Reports</i> [Internet]. 2021;7:2302–15. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egy.2021.04.038</p> <p>Messagie M, Boureima F, Matheys J, Sergeant N, Turcksin L, Macharis C, et al. Life Cycle Assessment of conventional and alternative small passenger vehicles in Belgium. 2010;32(0).</p> <p>Volkan P, Engin T, Babaarslan N, Burak G, Çalık. The Design and Manufacturing Process of an Electric Sport Car (EVT S1) Chassis. <i>Iran J Sci Technol Trans Mech Eng</i> [Internet]. 2019;45:103–13. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1007/s40997-019-00328-6</p>

Use stage

Hotspots	Electricity mix is a key parameter on environmental performance (Hawkins et al 2012)
	EV lifetime is largely reliant on use patterns (Hawkins et al 2012)
	Energy consumption is directly related to weight (Del Pero et al.)
Impact Range	50-80%
References	<p>Hawkins TR, Singh B, Majeau-Bettez G, Strømman AH. Comparative Environmental Life Cycle Assessment of Conventional and Electric Vehicles. J Ind Ecol. 2013;17(1):53–64.</p> <p>Pero F Del, Berzi L, Antonacci A, Delogu M. Automotive Lightweight Design : Simulation Modeling of Mass-Related Consumption for Electric Vehicles. 2020</p> <p>Gajendran and Clark (2003). Effect of Truck Operating Weight on Heavy-Duty Diesel Emissions.</p>

End-of-life

Hotspots	<p>Reusability and recyclability must be taken into consideration, especially for multi-material components (Stavropoulos et al 2019)</p>
	<p>The recovery of products counterbalances the drawbacks associated to an increase in energy consumption due to these operations (Aichberger et al 2020)</p>
	<p>Reclamation of energy-intensive aluminum would have a massive positive impact on the process: recovering 30% aluminum in the waste decreases the baseline GHG emissions from 61% against virgin production to 46% (Rinne et al, 2021)</p>
Impact Range	15-20%
References	<p>Aichberger C. Environmental Life Cycle Impacts of Automotive Batteries Based on a Literature Review. 2020;2019:1–27.</p> <p>Rinne M, Elomaa H, Porvali A, Lundstr M. Resources , Conservation & Recycling Simulation-based life cycle assessment for hydrometallurgical recycling of mixed LIB and NiMH waste. 2021;170(March).</p> <p>Stavropoulos P, Spetsieris A, Papacharalampopoulos A. A Circular Economy based Decision Support System for the Assembly/Disassembly of Multi-Material Components. Procedia CIRP [Internet]. 2020;85:48–53. Available from: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.09.033</p>

2. STEP 2. Eco-design strategies definition and set up

Considering the identified hotspots from the previous section, the most promising eco-design strategies are described on the following tables. Strategies can address one or more life cycle stages, and therefore, a specific section indicating the significance of each strategy on each of the life cycle stages is included, along with a description of the benefits the strategy allows for each that stage.

STRATEGY 1 A beneficial material selection			
DESCRIPTION			
A broader (than conventional) range of material families to address lightweighting should be considered for the chassis parts, from metals to hybrid materials			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	HIGH	HIGH	LOW
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
In the drive to improve efficiency and range of EVs, continuous research and innovation are required for the deployment of advanced light materials. In particular, significant yet affordable weight reduction is possible through the application of eco-design principles and the use of appropriate hybrid, multi-material solutions with integrated multiple functionalities to guarantee that all other performances (crashworthiness, reliability, durability etc.) are maintained.			
BENEFITS	Natural resource consumption reduction	Less energy consumption = less CO2 emissions	Less waste produced = less waste management
CONCLUSIONS			
Material selection should pursue an overall lifecycle emissions reduction, and not only focus on lightweighting			

STRATEGY 2 Considering the origin of the materials			
DESCRIPTION			
Lightweighting is the center key action to reduce the impact from electric vehicles, nevertheless, the origin of the materials needs to be also addressed. Avoidance of Critical raw materials (CRMs) must be considered			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>Raw material extraction, manufacturing, and assembly</p>	<p>Use stage</p>	<p>End-of-life</p>
SIGNIFICANCE	HIGH	ZERO	LOW
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
To avoid CRMs in alloys, increase use of recyclable materials, increase low intensity energy manufacturing options.			
BENEFITS	Natural resource consumption reduction / energy related impacts reduction		Waste treatment related impacts reduction. More straightforward recovery processes are less costly and have less environmental impacts
CONCLUSIONS			
Material substitution should pursue an overall lifecycle emissions reduction, and not only focus on lightweighting.			

STRATEGY 3 Design for lightweight			
DESCRIPTION			
Design will be optimized towards lightweight with the use of lightweight materials and structures through numerical simulations and the influence on the fatigue life of the component will be considered in the fatigue modelling			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	HIGH	HIGH	LOW
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
To consider manufacturing and assembly methods and tools to guarantee structural integrity, reliability and long service life by design for lightweight materials (e.g. through the understanding of failure mechanisms, of the impact of ageing phenomena and the effects of manufacturing processes on a microstructure level) including their experimental and model-based characterization.			
BENEFITS	Natural resource consumption reduction	Resource and energy consumption reduction	
CONCLUSIONS			
The impact of lightweighting on electric vehicles will reduce both vehicle and fuel cycle GHG emissions. This is extremely important to ensure the effectiveness of the strategy			

STRATEGY 4 Numerical strategies			
DESCRIPTION			
Numerical simulations will help understand mechanical behaviours for better performance and approach to circular use of material and products			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	LOW	HIGH	ZERO
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
Deployment of numerical simulation tools which will enable the adoption of circular economy strategies through appropriate optimization strategies.			
BENEFITS	More efficient resource use	Energy consumption reduction	
CONCLUSIONS			
Numerical strategies can enable the adoption of circular economy strategies			

STRATEGY 5 Design for maintainability			
DESCRIPTION			
Deepening on lifecycle extension, optimum maintenance capabilities and minimized repair time should be considered at the design stage			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	LOW	HIGH	MEDIUM
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
The challenge is to adopt such an integrated approach in order to reduce environmental impact and increase energy efficiency across the entire vehicle life-cycle from design, through production and use, to recovery.			
BENEFITS	More efficient resource use	Resource consumption reduction	Waste reduction and waste treatment related impacts reduction
CONCLUSIONS			
Design for maintenance will extend lifecycle of the EV, reducing resource consumption and waste treatment.			

STRATEGY 6 Design for EoL			
DESCRIPTION			
Definition of material recovery methods to enhance material scrap value			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	MEDIUM	ZERO	LOW
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
To study and include lightweight materials (both metallic and reinforced plastics) for automotive applications which are economically-viable including multi-material concepts that allow cost-effective material separation, recycling and recovery.			
BENEFITS	More efficient resource use		Waste treatment related impacts reduction
CONCLUSIONS			
Focus on the initial design to maximize environmental and economic performances through the promotion of the use of recyclable materials and the use of strategies that improve the modularity.			

STRATEGY 7 Lifecycle extension			
DESCRIPTION			
The assessment of the materials characteristics during the design stage will allow to maximize its useful life and maximize its efficiency			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>Raw material extraction, manufacturing, and assembly</p>	<p>Use stage</p>	<p>End-of-life</p>
SIGNIFICANCE	MEDIUM	HIGH	MEDIUM
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
To enhance material's properties which will allow the lifecycle extension allowing at the same time reuse, repair, repurposing, refurbishment, or remanufacturing strategies			
BENEFITS	More efficient resource use	Resource consumption reduction	Waste reduction and waste treatment related impacts reduction
CONCLUSIONS			
Extending useful life of the EV components, materials, and overall, the EV, will reduce environmental and economic impacts.			

STRATEGY 8 Value Return			
DESCRIPTION			
Thinking parts and components for a first and potential second useful life, also considering the recovery of materials, and specifically also CRMs			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	HIGH	ZERO	HIGH
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
Innovative options for end-of-life recovery, reuse, recycling and the optimized use of recycled materials and efficient remanufacturing. Recovering materials from waste in preparation for circular value retention as is predicted for CRMs			
BENEFITS	More efficient resource use		Waste reduction and waste treatment related impacts reduction
CONCLUSIONS			
Design for recovery of materials and potential components with a second useful life can reduce environmental impact significantly			

STRATEGY 9 Unity			
DESCRIPTION			
A holistic approach, where eco-design methodology will allow designers to participate in the decision process throughout the execution of the project. This will enhance implementation technologies and procedures by covering all life cycle stages.			
LIFE CYCLE STAGE	<p>End-of-life</p>		
SIGNIFICANCE	HIGH	HIGH	LOW
INNOVATIVE CHALLENGES			
Methods for the adoption of the circular economy and eco-design approach from the earliest stages of vehicle development, integrating product design and sustainable manufacturing, and including the optimal use of recycled and/or bio-resourced materials			
BENEFITS	Natural resource consumption reduction	Energy consumption reduction	Waste reduction and waste treatment related impacts reduction
CONCLUSIONS			
Eco-design should be applied at all stages of the project to benefit all life cycle stages			

3. STEP 3. Re-adaption of technological procedures to the selected strategies

To ensure a full adaptation of the strategies to the technical perspective and economic feasibility, step 3 and step 4 were nurtured from a collaborative webinar that took place on April 1st, 2022 with the participation of stakeholders, sub-divided by two different viewpoints and aided by a collaborative platform, the MIRO platform¹. The two groups were defined to better approach different mindsets to provide feedback on the strategies and their feasibility: Management and Design/Manufacturing.

Accordingly, a feasibility assessment has been brought about, during the webinar, to evaluate the technical and economic viability of each strategy. Figure 2 shows the area of the MIRO platform that was used to vote the technical feasibility and economic viability.

¹ www.miro.com

Figure 2. Strategies feasibility assessment

Attendants had a total of 18 available votes and could only vote once for each of the aspects of each strategy. In total there were 8 attendants participating on the voting session.

Results from the feasibility assessment are presented on Table 1. Also, the technical and economic conclusions are included. These are based on the fact that the lack of votes is actually a negative vote for that aspect/strategy. Therefore, 4 or more votes are required to consider that strategy as feasible/viable.

Table 1. Feasibility assessment results

Code	Strategy	Technical feasibility	Economic viability	Technical conclusion	Economic conclusion	Considered?
S1	A beneficial material selection	3	4	Not Feasible	Viable	Yes, with caution on technical feasibility
S2	Considering the origin of the materials	6	4	Feasible	Viable	Yes
S3	Design for lightweight	8	7	Feasible	Viable	Yes
S4	Numerical strategies	5	4	Feasible	Viable	Yes
S5	Design for maintainability	5	4	Feasible	Viable	Yes
S6	Design for End-of-Life (reuse and recycling)	3	2	Not Feasible	Not Viable	No
S7	Lifecycle extension	1	1	Not Feasible	Not Viable	No
S8	Value Return	3	6	Not Feasible	Viable	Yes, with caution on technical feasibility
S9	Unity	4	3	Feasible	Not Viable	Yes, with caution on economic viability

The final list of strategies to be considered is presented in Table 2. Even though, Strategy 6 is considered nor feasible or viable, it is included on the list because in the next step, during the brainstorming on specific actions, one or more actions were defined within this strategy.

Table 2. Final list of strategies

S1*	A beneficial material selection
S2	Considering the origin of the materials
S3	Design for lightweight
S4	Numerical strategies
S5	Design for maintainability
S6	Design for End-of-Life (reuse and recycling)
S7new*	Value Return
S8new**	Unity
* With caution on technical feasibility ** With caution on economic viability	

3.1 STEP 4. Definition of concrete eco-design actions

Continuing the collaborative webinar from step 3, on step 4, webinar attendants proposed specific eco-design actions through the MIRO collaborative platform. Figure 3 depicts the brainstorming session on the MIRO platform.

Figure 3. MIRO platform - Brainstorm on actions

After brainstorming, all feedback was gathered and studied to assemble the list of most noticeable eco-design actions to be considered during the Fatigue4Light project. Table 3 shows the list of specific eco-design actions.

Table 3. List of eco-design actions

Action	Description
Action 1	Use of recycled and recyclable materials for the different demonstrators
Action 2	Use of lightweight materials to reduce whole EV weight, e.g. HSS steel to reduce chassis weight
Action 3	Adopt a "design for recycling" approach by using easy recoverable and recyclable materials e.g. one family of aluminium alloy
Action 4	Introduce optimal design for energy efficiency and lightweight, e.g. consider the type of vehicle and its use pattern to design optimized parts of the EV
Action 5	Use numerical modelling to optimize part design. E.g. topology optimization.
Action 6	Introduce optimal design for life extension, e.g. material coating for prolonged life and improved maintainability, Increase of fatigue properties of welded assemblies...
Action 7	Adopt a "design for disassembly" approach by including the use joining elements that can easily be removed
Action 8	Reduction of Critical Raw Materials from alloys
Action 9	Adopt a lifecycle perspective to obtain longer term choices and improve the entire EV environmental impact

In the interest of following up on the application of the eco-design actions throughout the project, bimonthly meetings and data gathering will be arranged with the responsible partners.

3.1.1 AHP assisted Eco-design actions

The final step is to have a concept design. This concept design will be the starting point for the designing in detail that, supported by the LCA, will iterate until obtaining eco-designed chassis parts that achieve the environmental objectives of the project. The concept design considers the ranking of the eco-designs through Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP).

The AHP process involves weighting paired criteria, breaking decision making into small pieces, and pair by pair, solve the bigger decision problem. AHP is constituted by two phases: first the hierarchy tree definition and second, the numerical evaluation of the tree. Fatigue4Light's decision tree is presented on Table 4.

Table 4. Fatigue4Light AHP decision tree

Group	Strategy	Actions
Circular design models	A beneficial material selection	Use of recycled and recyclable materials for the different demonstrators Reduction of Critical Raw Materials from alloys
	Considering the origin of the materials	Adopt a lifecycle perspective to obtain longer term choices and improve the entire EV environmental impact
Optimal use models	Design for lightweight	Use of lightweight materials to reduce whole EV weight, e.g. HSS steel to reduce chassis weight Introduce optimal design for energy efficiency and lightweight, e.g. consider the type of vehicle and its use pattern to design optimized parts of the EV
	Design for maintainability	Introduce optimal design for life extension, e.g. material coating for prolonged life and improved maintainability, Increase of fatigue properties of welded assemblies...
Value recovery models	Value Return	Adopt a "design for disassembly" approach by including the use joining elements that can easily be removed
	Design for EoL	Adopt a "design for recycling" approach by using easy recoverable and recyclable materials e.g. one family of aluminium alloy
Circular support	Numerical strategies	Use numerical modelling to optimize part design. E.g topology optimization.
	Unity	

The evaluation of the tree is based on a pair-wise comparison, and it is made bottom-up, starting with the comparison of the alternatives of the sub-criteria of the last level (in this case Actions) and ending with the first branch, that in this case, is the strategies. The scheme proposed by the author of the AHP Methodology, Thomas Saaty, is presented in Table 5 as a translation of judgments into numbers.

Table 5. AHP Judgment scores

Judgment	Score
Equal	1
Moderately better	3
Definitely better	5
Very strongly better	7
Absolutely better	9

AHP internal scoring matrix for the eco-design actions is presented in Table 6. And Table 7 presents the resulting score for the actions, as a result of the average of the normalized scores for the action on that line in the matrix.

The methodology also offers a consistency ratio as a verification of consistency in the decision process for all the scores. For the actions scoring matrix the consistency was above the recommended 10% for 9 alternatives. This may be due to human inconsistency in decisions, which does not mean error, but a bias. To correct the consistency ratio, the final score has been linearized to a 5% consistency ratio, already considered in Table 7.

Table 6. AHP actions score matrix

	Action 1	Action 2	Action 3	Action 4	Action 5	Action 6	Action 7	Action 8	Action 9
Action 1	1	1/5	1	1/3	3	1/3	3	5	1/5
Action 2	5	1	5	1	7	1/5	5	5	1/5
Action 3	1	1/5	1	1/5	5	1/5	3	5	1/5
Action 4	3	1	5	1	3	1	7	7	1/3
Action 5	1/3	1/7	1/5	1/3	1	1/5	3	3	1/5
Action 6	3	5	5	1	5	1	5	7	1/3
Action 7	1/3	1/5	1/3	1/7	1/3	1/5	1	3	1/7
Action 8	1/5	1/5	1/5	1/7	1/3	1/7	1/3	1	1/7
Action 9	5	5	5	3	5	3	7	7	1

Table 7. Actions scores

Action	Linearized Score
1. Use of recycled and recyclable materials for the different demonstrators	0,021
2. Use of lightweight materials to reduce whole EV weight, e.g. HSS steel to reduce chassis weight	0,047
3. Adopt a "design for recycling" approach by using easy recoverable and recyclable materials e.g. one family of aluminium alloy	0,022
4. Introduce optimal design for energy efficiency and lightweight, e.g. consider the type of vehicle and its use pattern to design optimized parts of the EV	0,049
5. Use numerical modelling to optimize part design. E.g. topology optimization.	0,014
6. Introduce optimal design for life extension, e.g. material coating for prolonged life and improved maintainability, Increase of fatigue properties of welded assemblies...	0,060
7. Adopt a "design for disassembly" approach by including the use joining elements that can easily be removed	0,029
8. Reduction of Critical Raw Materials from alloys	0,019
9. Adopt a lifecycle perspective to obtain longer term choices and improve the entire EV environmental impact	0,096

Following step is to score the first branch, which was done during the webinar using AhaSlides platform to allow all participants to score each of the paired alternatives. Figure 4 depicts one of the slides prepared on the platform for the scoring of the strategies, and how the scores were being registered at the moment.

The AhaSlides platform was considered as a useful tool to simplify the process of comparing pair by pair the 9 alternative strategies and also to collect the results from all participants in an orderly manner. Since the slides were prepared before the feasibility evaluation, all 9 alternatives were evaluated. However, for this report, tables have already been corrected to the 8 final strategies.

4. How significant are Numerical strategies, compared to:

Menu

4 8/50

Figure 4. AHP strategy scoring on AhaSlides

AHP scoring matrix for the eco-design strategies has been compiled from the answers on AhaSlides and the mode for each of the questions was considered for the matrix. Answers to the paired evaluation from the participants are presented in Table 8 and the scoring matrix with the mode value in Table 9. Whenever the mode was not available, a value of 1 has been considered. Later on, Table 10 presents the final scores for the strategies.

Table 8. AhaSlides scoring compilation

Alternative strategy	Strategy for comparison	Participant 1	Participant 2	Participant 3	Participant 4	Participant 5	Participant 6	Mode
1	2	7	1	5	9	3	1	1
1	3	9	1	1	9	1/3	3	1
1	4	3	5	3	9	3	3	3
1	5	3	5	7	9	3	3	3
1	6	9	9	1	3	1	1	1
1	7	3	5	1	7	1	7	1
1	8	5	1	1	3	1	1	1
1	9	3	1/3	3	7	1	1	1
2	1	7	1	1/5	9	1/3	1/9	#N/A
2	3	9	1/5	1/3	1	1/5	1/9	1/5
2	4	3	1/3	1/3	3	1/3	1/9	1/3
2	5	3	1/3	1	9	1/3	1/9	1/3
2	6	7	1/3	1/3	9	1/3	5	1/3
2	7	9	1/3	1/3	1	1/3	5	1/3
2	8	3	1/3	1/3	3	1	7	1/3

2	9	3	1/3	1/3	5	1	1	1
3	1	9	1	1	9	3	9	9
3	2	3	3	3	1	3	1/3	3
3	4	3	1	1	3	3	7	3
3	5	1	3	3	1/3	1/3	1	1
3	6	9	7	1	1/5	1/3	1	1
3	7	5	3	1	1/7	1/3	3	3
3	8	3	3	3	1/5	1	1	3
3	9	3	5	3	1	1	1	1
4	1	3	1/3	1/3	1	1/3	1	1/3
4	2	3	3	3	1/3	1	1/9	3
4	3	3	3	1/3	3	1/3	5	3
4	5	3	3	1	1/3	1/3	1	1
4	6	1	1/3	1	1/5	1/3	1	1
4	7	3	1	1	1/5	1/3	1	1
4	8	3	3	1	1/3	1	3	3
4	9	1	1	3	3	1	1	1
5	1	5	1/3	1/3	5	1	3	5
5	2	1	1/3	1	1	3	1	1
5	3	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	1
5	4	5	1/3	1/3	1/3	3	1	1/3
5	6	1	1/3	1/3	1	1	5	1
5	7	1	1/3	1	1/3	1	9	1
5	8	1	1/3	1/3	3	1	5	1
5	9	1	1/3	1	3	1	1	1
6	1	9	1/3	1/3	9	1	3	9
6	2	5	1/3	1	1/3	3	5	5
6	3	1	1/3	1	1	1	1/3	1
6	4	1	1/3	1/3	1	3	1	1
6	5	1	1/3	1	1	1	3	1
6	7	9	1/3	1	1	1	3	1
6	8	9	1/3	1/3	1	1	1/3	1/3
6	9	3	1/3	1	1	1	1	1
7	1	9	3	1/3	1	1	3	3
7	2	3	3	1	1	3	3	3
7	3	3	3	1/3	3	1	1/9	3
7	4	9	3	1/3	1/5	3	1	3
7	5	9	1	1	1	1	9	1
7	6	3	3	1	9	1	3	3
7	8	3	3	1/3	9	1	1/3	1/3
7	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
8	1	9	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	3	1/3
8	2	5	1/3	1	1/3	1	1/9	1
8	3	1	1/3	1/3	1/5	1/3	1/9	1/3

8	4	1	1/3	1/3	1/3	3	1	1/3
8	5	1	1/3	1	1/3	1	1	1
8	6	9	1/3	1	1/5	1/3	1/3	1/3
8	7	3	1/3	1	1/5	1/3	3	3
8	9	3	1/3	1	1	1	1	1
9	1	5	3	1/5	5	1/3	1	5
9	2	1	3	1	5	1	1	1
9	3	1	3	1/3	7	1/3	1	1
9	4	5	3	1/3	7	1	1	1
9	5	1	3	1	5	1/3	1	1
9	6	1	3	1	3	1/5	1	1
9	7	1	3	1	5	1/3	1	1
9	8	1	3	1/3	3	1	1	1

Table 9. AHP strategy score matrix

	A beneficial material selection	Considering the origin of the materials	Design for lightweight	Numerical strategies	Design for maintainability	Design for End-of-Life (reuse and recycling)	Value Return	Unity
A beneficial material selection	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	1
Considering the origin of the materials	1	1	1/5	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1
Design for lightweight	1	5	1	3	1	1	3	1
Numerical strategies	1/3	3	1/3	1	1	1	3	1
Design for maintainability	1/3	3	1	1	1	1	1	1
Design for End-of-Life (reuse and recycling)	1	3	1	1	1	1	1/3	1
Value Return	1	3	1/3	1/3	1	3	1	1
Unity	5	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 10. Strategy scores

Strategy	Linearized Score
A beneficial material selection	0,115
Considering the origin of the materials	0,055
Design for lightweight	0,131
Numerical strategies	0,088
Design for maintainability	0,081
Design for End-of-Life (reuse and recycling)	0,081
Value Return	0,091
Unity	0,113

Consistency ratio for the strategy score was also higher than the recommended by the literature and therefore linearized to a 5% consistency ratio. Last step within the AHP methodology is to obtain a ranked list of eco-design actions, and for this end, a final score is calculated on Table 11.

Finally, a ranked list of actions is presented in Table 12, from the most relevant to the least value.

Table 11. AHP final score

Strategy	Strategy score	Actions	Action score	Final score
A beneficial material selection	0,155	Use of recycled and recyclable materials for the different demonstrators	0,021	0,003
		Reduction of Critical Raw Materials from alloys	0,019	0,003
Considering the origin of the materials	0,055	Adopt a lifecycle perspective to obtain longer term choices and improve the entire EV environmental impact	0,096	0,005
Design for lightweight	0,177	Use of lightweight materials to reduce whole EV weight, e.g. HSS steel to reduce chassis weight	0,047	0,008
		Introduce optimal design for lightweight, e.g. consider the type of vehicle and its use pattern to design optimized parts of the EV	0,049	0,009
Numerical strategies	0,119	Use numerical modelling to optimize part design. E.g. topology optimization.	0,014	0,002
Design for maintainability	0,110	Introduce optimal design for life extension, e.g. material coating for prolonged life and improved maintainability, Increase of fatigue properties of welded assemblies...	0,060	0,007
Design for End-of-Life (reuse and recycling)	0,110	Adopt a "design for recycling" approach by using easy recoverable and recyclable materials e.g. one family of aluminium alloy	0,022	0,002
Value Return	0,122	Adopt a "design for disassembly" approach by including the use joining elements that can easily be removed	0,029	0,001
Unity	0,152			

Table 12. Ranked list of actions

Ranked Actions
Use numerical modelling to optimize part design. E.g. topology optimization.
Adopt a "design for recycling" approach by using easy recoverable and recyclable materials e.g. one family of aluminium alloy
Reduction of Critical Raw Materials from alloys
Use of recycled and recyclable materials for the different demonstrators
Adopt a "design for disassembly" approach by including the use joining elements that can easily be removed
Adopt a lifecycle perspective to obtain longer term choices and improve the entire EV environmental impact
Introduce optimal design for life extension, e.g. material coating for prolonged life and improved maintainability, Increase of fatigue properties of welded assemblies...
Use of lightweight materials to reduce whole EV weight, e.g. HSS steel to reduce chassis weight
Introduce optimal design for energy efficiency and lightweight, e.g. consider the type of vehicle and its use pattern to design optimized parts of the EV

4. CONCLUSIONS

The eco-design methodology has allowed to determine, at first, the most relevant issues related to the environmental performance of EVs, that at the same time, has supported the establishment of the most appropriate eco-design strategies.

In addition, inputs from partners' participants of the webinar are of high value, including the definition of specific eco-design actions, the evaluation of feasibility of the strategies and the AHP score for the strategies as well.

Main final result from the AHP methodology has allowed to obtain a ranked list of actions, that will facilitate the application of eco-design throughout Fatigue4Light project.

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